

Behavioral Skills Training Protocol

Instruction

1. The practitioner provided instruction including a purpose statement to the confederate by saying:
“Today, I’m going to teach you how to serve as a confederate in a concurrent operant analysis (COA) session. A COA is an assessment that evaluates choice behavior in client. In this assessment, we present many different types of options to our clients and see which ones they choose. You will be serving the role as confederate which means you will offer attention to your client. The purpose of this is to see if they choose to allocate towards choices that provide access to your attention.”
2. The practitioner then asked if the confederate had any questions.

Model

1. Following instruction, the practitioner then modeled the role as the COA confederate.
2. The practitioner modeled by sitting on the correct side of the (insert area).
3. With another person role playing as the client, the practitioner provided the client with high-quality attention.
4. The practitioner did not ask questions or place any demands on the client.
5. If there were materials associated such as high-preferred tangibles, the practitioner allowed the client to play as they would like and engaged with the items as the client asked.
6. The practitioner did not use any statements that tried to encourage a client to come to their side such as: “Play with me!” or “Come over this way.”

Role Play

1. The practitioner then asked the COA confederate to role play their part for the COA.
2. The practitioner conducted several trials in which they came to the side that COA confederate was on to ensure that the COA confederate offered appropriate attention.
3. The practitioner also went to the opposite side to ensure that the COA confederate did not try to encourage them to come to their side.

Feedback

1. Follow the role play, the practitioner provided feedback about the COA’s confederate where appropriate. For example, if the COA confederate asked a question of the client, the practitioner reminded the COA confederate to refrain from asking questions.